

HeAL9000: an Intelligent Rehabilitation Robot for Physical and Cognitive Interaction

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Abstract—The introduction of robotic platforms for rehabilitation allows delivering highly intensive, repeatable and accurate motion therapy, constantly monitoring the patient to provide the correct level of assistance. Robot-aided rehabilitation requires a physical interaction with the patient, but generally does not include a cognitive interaction. From the analysis of the literature, it is worth noticing that robotic platforms providing both physical and cognitive support to patients have not been proposed so far. The aim of the HeAL9000 project is to develop and validate an intelligent robot for the rehabilitation of MSDs, integrating both physical and cognitive interaction modalities to reproduce conventional therapist-patient ones.

Index Terms—Robot-aided rehabilitation, Physical interaction, Cognitive interaction, MSDs

I. INTRODUCTION

The adoption of robotic devices in rehabilitation is widely increased in recent years, since robots have the ability to deliver highly intensive, repeatable and accurate motion therapy for neurological and musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) [1]. The goal of rehabilitation is the functional recovery of the body area of interest, the restoration of the functional range of motion and the recovery of muscle strength. Robot-aided motor therapy has further advantages, such as the possibility of objectifying patient performance, modulating in an appropriate way the level of assistance and providing feedback during treatment [2]. The first clinical study was carried out in 1997 using the commercial robot MIT-MANUS on post-stroke patients, to evaluate the effectiveness of robot-aided rehabilitation. In more recent studies, robotic assistance has been dynamically changed on the basis of patient biomechanical and psychophysiological state [4]. However, robotic platforms capable of providing both physical and cognitive support to the patient with neurological or MSDs did not emerge from the analysis of the state-of-the-art [3]. For these reasons, the Healthcare Agents and Learning robots (HeAL9000) national project, funded by Regione Lazio and started in June 2020, aims at developing and validating in a real scenario a smart robotic platform to deliver rehabilitation to patients affected by

This work was supported partly by partly by Regione Lazio with the HeAL9000 project (CUP: B84I20001880002) and partly by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme with the ODIN project (CUP: C85F21000670006).

MSDs, able to promote the patient’s motor recovery through a human-robot interaction that exploits the same communication channels adopted in therapist-patient interaction, i.e. verbal, physical, cognitive.

II. ROBOT-AIDED REHABILITATION: A NOVEL APPROACH

The role of a therapist is paramount in motor rehabilitation. The healthcare operator has to establish a physical and cognitive relationship with the patient and his intervention cannot ignore the patient’s clinical and emotional state. The HeAL9000 project aims at replicating the interaction between therapist and patient, established during a conventional rehabilitation session, to improve the effectiveness of the rehabilitation treatment. To do this, the HeAL9000 robotic platform will (i) consist of a service robot capable of replicating the behavior of the human therapist thanks to the use of Machine Learning and Learning by Demonstration techniques; (ii) have a highly adaptive behavior with respect to the characteristics of the patient to the multimodal monitoring of the patient; (iii) establish physical and cognitive interaction with the patient, similar to the one observed in the combination therapist-patient. It has the twofold purpose of motivating the patient to actively participate in the treatment and strongly personalizing the rehabilitation session according to the physical and cognitive state of the patient.

III. PATIENT-THERAPIST INTERACTION MODEL

Starting from the analysis of the conventional rehabilitation sessions, it is possible to distinguish the roles played by the patient and the therapist [5]. They assume dynamic behaviors based on circumstances and stimuli that the two exchange reciprocally. At the beginning of the rehabilitation session, the therapist demonstrates to the patient the task to be performed, also through his/her own body and the patient does not perform any movement. However, it is possible that the patient asks for clarifications about the activity to be performed. At the end of the demonstration, the therapist starts the observation phase. At this time, the patient plays the role of the main actor as he/she is asked to perform the proposed exercise independently. In turn, the therapist monitors the subject and encourages and/or warn him/her to carry out the assigned

motor task in the best way. Whenever the therapist decides to intervene to correct any patient error and/or the patient complains of pain or fatigue, the role of the therapist turns into the helper one. In this context, the real interaction between the two actors begins and takes place. As soon as the exercise is completed, the cycle continues until the rehabilitation session is completed. In order to develop an effective robot-aided system for rehabilitation, it is necessary to implement such roles onto a robotic platform, able to handle both physical and cognitive interactions, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Proof-of-concept of patient-robot interaction.

A. Physical interaction

The robotic platform is able to play one role among demonstrator, observer and helper, as reported in Fig. 1. In the first scenario, the robot demonstrates the motor task to be performed by the patient. When the patient tries to execute the task, the robot constantly evaluates the motor performance of the patient exploiting RGB-D cameras and skeleton tracking algorithms. In the helper role, the robot guides the limb of the patient in correctly executing the assigned task. To do this, it is essential to model the physical interactions of the rehabilitation treatment to tune the behavior of the robotic platform. Dynamic Movement Primitives [6] allows encoding the therapist-patient physical interaction to retarget the recorded motions onto the robotic platform.

B. Cognitive interaction

The cognitive dimension of the therapist-patient interaction is managed by a dedicated set of modules devoted to the acquisition of input from the environment (from verbal input

Fig. 2. The workflow behind the cognitive interaction

to physical stimuli), to the tracking of the whole dialogue and the planning of individual reactions (Fig. 2). When a verbal input is provided by the patient, the neural architecture discussed in [7] is applied for *Speech to Text* transcription. Let us consider a patient during the exercise who says "My arm hurts" to express some difficulties due to the requested movements. Content is processed by the *Natural Language Understanding* module that implements the inductive method described in [9]: here the semantic interpretation in terms of Frames Semantics [8] that models input sentences into meaning representation graphs is also coupled with the recognition of the user intent. The semantic graph is then provided to the *Dialogue Management Module* used to recognize user states on *Dialogue State Tracking*, to plan the robot reactions to the input, to update current states, accordingly, and finally to compile the requested linguistics output. In the workflow, the resulting semantic frame is BODY_MOVEMENT that asks the patient to move its arm (the BODY_PART as argument of the input frame) for a given DURATION, i.e. a while. The output frame is compiled by the *Natural Language Generation* module as the sentence "Lift it up for a while" that feeds the robot text-to-speech module. The cognitive architecture in the HeAL9000 integrates inductive modules such as the language understanding one with knowledge-based components, dependent on domain specific pragmatic (e.g dialogue state tracking) resources as well as medical knowledge bases.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The HeAL9000 project has the ambition to design, develop and validate in an operative environment a robotic system for rehabilitation capable of replicating physical and cognitive interaction with the patient. This objective poses numerous technological, scientific and ethical challenges. The results may reveal whether and to what extent the use of a robot integrating physical and cognitive capabilities can be a valid tool to improve the effectiveness of rehabilitation treatment in patients affected by MSDs.

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